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The linguistic features of legal language

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Abstract: This article analyzes the linguistic features of legal language based on a comprehensive approach. In the course of the research, the lexical, grammatical and stylistic aspects of legal texts, in particular, terminological accuracy, level of formality, normativity, complex syntactic constructions and the predominant use of passive forms are studied. The semantic load of modal verbs, conditional constructions and prescriptive units in legal discourse is also analyzed. The article substantiates that the main task of legal language is to express legal relations in a clear, unambiguous and interpretation-free manner. The results of the research are of scientific and practical importance in the fields of law, linguistics and translation studies and can be used in the analysis and translation of legal texts.

Keywords: legal language, legal discourse, linguistic features, terminology, formal style, normativity, syntactic complexity, modal verbs, legal text, prescriptive units.

Introduction.

Legal language is one of the main tools that ensure order, justice and legal stability in society. Through laws, regulatory legal acts, court decisions and official contracts, legal language regulates social relations and defines clear boundaries of legal relations between the state and citizens. Therefore, legal language is not only a means of communication, but also an important mechanism for the exercise of legal power.

The uniqueness of legal language is manifested in its fundamental difference from ordinary everyday speech. In this type of language, clarity, consistency and unambiguousness are of paramount importance, since every word, phrase or grammatical construction in a legal text can have legal consequences. In this regard, the limited use of synonyms in legal language, the widespread use of complex syntactic structures, passive forms and modal verbs is not accidental, but arises from the

mandatory and prescriptive nature of the legal norm.

In the current era of increasing globalization and legal integration processes, in-depth study of the linguistic features of legal language is becoming increasingly important. International treaties, transnational legal documents and multilingual legal communication put the issue of correct interpretation and accurate translation of legal texts on the agenda. This creates the need to analyze legal language not only from the point of view of jurisprudence, but also based on linguistic and discursive approaches. This article aims to reveal the structure, semantic load and functional properties of legal texts by analyzing the linguistic features of legal language. The results of the study are significant in that they serve to improve the understanding of legal discourse, the interpretation and translation of legal texts.

Source analysis:

The issue of linguistic features of legal language is one of the current scientific areas formed at the intersection of linguistics, jurisprudence and discourse analysis. Research on this issue is mainly aimed at highlighting the structural, semantic and pragmatic aspects of legal texts, and different approaches have been developed within different scientific schools.

In Western linguistic schools, legal language is interpreted primarily as a special (professional) discourse. Researchers such as D. Mellinkoff, P. Tiersma and R. Wydick point out the complexity of legal language, archaic units, Latin phrases and syntactic devices based on normativity as its main features. In their studies, along with the desire for clarity and unambiguity, legal language is also critically highlighted as a closed system that is difficult for the average reader to understand.

In the research conducted within the framework of functional linguistics, legal language is interpreted as a type of prescriptive speech. Based on the functional approach of M. Halliday, the ideational, interpersonal and textual functions of legal texts are analyzed, and the role of modal verbs (shall, must, may) in expressing legal obligations and permissions is especially emphasized. This approach serves as an important methodological basis for revealing the social function of legal language.

In the research conducted by Russian and CIS scientists, legal language is studied

within the framework of a more formal-business style. Scientists such as V. V. Vinogradov, L. A. Kapanadze, N. D. Arutyunova note the primacy of terminological stability, templated constructions and complex syntax in legal texts. In their works, the normative and communicative functions of legal language are analyzed in their interrelation.

In research in the field of translation studies, the linguistic features of legal language are of particular importance. In particular, the problems of equivalence of legal terms, cultural-legal differences and syntactic adaptation have been deeply analyzed by scholars such as P. Šarčević and S. Cao. These studies demonstrate the importance of a linguistic approach in interpreting legal texts in a multilingual environment.

Although legal language issues have been relatively little studied in Uzbek linguistics, research on formal-style texts, terminology and documentary language serves as an important theoretical basis for this area. Studies on the formation of legal terms, their standardization and functional characteristics help to reveal the national characteristics of the legal language.

In general, an analysis of the existing scientific literature shows that the linguistic characteristics of the legal language require a multifaceted and interdisciplinary approach. At the same time, studies aimed at analyzing the legal language in a comprehensive manner - in lexical, grammatical and discursive aspects - have not been sufficiently systematized. This article is of scientific importance in that it is aimed at filling this gap.

Analytical discussion.

In the process of analyzing the linguistic features of legal language, it becomes clear that it is not only a set of special terms, but also a form of expression of legal thought and normative consciousness through language. Legal texts are formed subject to the requirements of logical rigor and normative clarity, which creates complexity and formality in their linguistic structure. It is this aspect that is manifested as one of the main features that distinguishes legal language from everyday speech.

The analysis shows that the lexical choice in legal language is not random, but is

based on strict normative norms. The stability and repeated use of terms serve to ensure the unambiguous meaning of the legal text. However, this situation in some cases leads to the fact that legal texts are stylistically heavy and difficult to perceive. This complexity of the legal language is associated with its functional necessity, which is aimed at minimizing the possibility of different interpretations of legal norms. At the grammatical level, the predominance of complex syntactic constructions and passive forms is observed in legal texts. This phenomenon allows us to express the legal norm as general and mandatory, without personalizing the legal subject. The widespread use of modal verbs clearly defines the categories of legal obligation, prohibition and permission. In particular, units of a prescriptive nature reveal the essence of legal language, expressing orders and obligations.

From a pragmatic point of view, legal language reflects not equality, but normative priority in communication. The relationship between the author and the addressee of a legal text is not symmetrical: the legislator or judicial body appears as a subject giving orders through the legal text. This situation strengthens the demand for objectivity and freedom from personal relationships in legal discourse. At the same time, the need for simplification and openness of legal language in modern legal communication is growing. The concept of “plain legal language” is aimed at making legal texts understandable to the general public, and this approach is being formed as an alternative to the traditional complexity of legal language. However, this process raises the issue of maintaining legal clarity and normative rigor as an urgent problem.

Thus, the linguistic features of legal language reflect a balance between two main opposing tendencies - clarity and comprehensibility. Ensuring this balance remains one of the most important tasks of legal linguistics. This analytical discussion shows the need to interpret legal language not only as a static system, but also as a communicative phenomenon that is constantly evolving under the influence of social needs.

Conclusion.

This study was aimed at analyzing the linguistic features of legal language based on a comprehensive approach. The conducted analyses showed that legal language, with its lexical, grammatical and pragmatic aspects, constitutes a separate system, and

its formation is directly related to the mandatory and normative nature of legal norms. Terminological clarity, formality and unambiguousness are paramount in legal texts, and these features are of great importance in ensuring the stability of legal relations.

The results of the study confirmed that the complex syntactic structures of legal language, passive constructions and the widespread use of modal verbs serve to express the generally binding, not personal, nature of the legal norm. At the same time, the predominance of prescriptive units in legal discourse revealed the communicative function of legal language, expressing orders and obligations. The analysis showed that the linguistic complexity of the legal language is not its disadvantage, but its functional necessity. However, in the conditions of modern legal communication, the issue of increasing the intelligibility of legal texts is becoming increasingly urgent. This requires a scientific justification of the problem of using simplified language tools while maintaining legal clarity. In conclusion, the study of the linguistic features of the legal language allows for a deeper understanding of legal discourse, correct interpretation and effective translation of legal texts. The results of this study are of theoretical and practical importance in the fields of law, linguistics and translation studies, and serve as a methodological basis for further scientific research aimed at further improving the legal language.

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